

Yield loss caused by leaffolder (LF) damage alone and combined with yellow stem borer (YSB) damage

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LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Gn.) and YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Wlk.) are major pests of rice in Gujarat. We estimated yield loss caused by LF infestation alone and in combination with YSB infestation during 1986 summer and kharif seasons. Commercially grown cultivar GR11 was the test variety. Fifty plants were observed periodically for infestation by

Regression of grain yield on LF infestation (a) and on combined LF and YSB infestation in summer (b) and in kharif (c) Gujarat, India, 1986.

LF alone and 50 for infestation by LF and YSB (whiteheads). Grain was collected from individual plants.

Regressions of grain yield by percentage LF infestation alone and percentage LF and YSB infestation were calculated (see figure). For every unit of

increase in LF infestation alone, yield decreased 1.4% during summer and 1.46% during kharif. For every unit of increase in LF and YSB infestation, yield decreased 1.12% during summer and 1.27% during kharif. □

Spiders in Madhya Pradesh, India

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Weekly surveys were made of spiders contributing to rice pest control from the nursery stage until harvest in the rice zone (Chhattishgarh region) of Madhya Pradesh during 1984-86 rabi (Jan-May) and kharif (Jul-Nov). Nearly 10 ha were sampled weekly. At the early crop stages, spiders were collected by 100 sweeps/ha of a sweep net swinging through 180° with a 150-cm radius and covering $350 \text{ cm}^2/\text{sweep}$. From panicle initiation onward, spiders were sampled using $70 \times 30\text{-cm}$ plastic bags. The bag was held horizontally beside the rice hill to be sampled, and the hill was struck firmly four times so that spiders fell into the bag. About 250 hills were sampled

Spiders recorded in Madhya Pradesh, India, 1984-86.

Spider	Family
<i>Neoscona</i> sp.	Araneidae
<i>Runcinia</i> sp.	Thomisidae
<i>Thornisus</i> sp.	Thomisidae
<i>Arctosa</i> sp.	Lycosidae
<i>Pardosa</i> sp.	Lycosidae
<i>Tetragnatha</i> sp.	Tetragnathidae
<i>Oxyopes</i> sp.	Oxyopidae
<i>Uloborid</i> sp.	Uloboridae
<i>Eusparassid</i> sp.	Eusparassidae
<i>Aelurillus</i> sp.	Salticidae
<i>Bianor</i> sp.	Salticidae
<i>Hyllus</i> sp.	Salticidae
<i>Thyene</i> sp.	Salticidae

each week. The Commonwealth Agricultural Bureaux International Institute of Entomology at the British Museum, London, identified the spiders (see table). This is the first record of spiders in Chhattishgarh region. □

Rice thrips, a new rice pest in Northern Telangana, India

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Incidence of rice thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagn), hitherto a minor pest of rice, was severe in the Jul-Nov crop in the Northern Telangana zone of Andhra Pradesh, especially during Aug-Sep. Incidence also was severe in about 100 ha of rice planted during the last week of Aug. Farmers in this area normally sow in Jun and transplant in Jul. In 1986, sowing was delayed by the late onset of monsoon. The normal cropping pattern is rice - rice.

Thrips damage was severe during a prolonged dry spell after the onset of the monsoon. The late rice was more prone to pest infestation than the early crop. Typical symptoms were inward leaf rolling, wilting, and fine yellowish or silvery longitudinal streaks developing from the margin to the midrib.

Thrips damage was severe in transplanted Surekha, followed by IR50, WGL 22245, BPT1235, and WGL 3996. Incidence was lowest in WGL 44645.

One-month-old nurseries of IET1994, IR20, IET9553, IR36, IET8906, IET8559, TN1, and IET9999 were severely infested when sown in late Aug. Temperatures during Aug were $23.9\text{--}32.2^\circ\text{C}$, with a mean rainfall of 70.8 mm. The same cultures transplanted in plots suffered pest

incidence in Oct, when temperatures were 20.7-32.7 °C with a mean rainfall of 18.2 mm. In general, thrips damage was high after heavy rains followed by a prolonged (40-45 d) dry spell. □

***Heliothis armigera* development and damage to rice**

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Heliothis armigera (Hübner), a highly polyphagous insect, has occasionally been reported as a rice pest. Larvae from six host plants — maize, sorghum, wheat, pigeonpea, mungbean, and tobacco — were reared on the hosts. Upon emergence, mated pairs from each host were caged in 12- × 39-cm mylar tubes with 30- and 75-d-old IR1917-3-17 rice plants. Honey solution (10%) was added in a wick receptacle.

Moths laid eggs on the rice leaves and fully exerted panicles for 5 d. Growth and development of *H. armigera* and potential damage of rice panicles by larvae were determined.

The six phenotypes of *Heliothis* laid more eggs on 75-d-old plants, with 88% of the eggs laid on grains between the lemma and palea (see table). The higher

Development and gain damage by 6 *Heliothis armigera* phenotypes^a on IR1917-3-17 rice.^b IRRI greenhouse, Nov 1985-May 1986.

Phenotype source	Ovipositional preference ^c (no. of eggs/plant)		Egg hatch (%)	Larval wt (mg)	Growth index ^d	Adult		Damaged grains ^e (%)
	30 DAS	75 DAS				Wt (mg)	Longevity (d)	
	Pigeonpea	6 c				62 c	87 a	
Mungbean	8 c	88 b	90 a	81 c	-	-	28 b	
Tobacco	6 c	59 c	88 a	79 c	-	-	20 c	
Maize	26 a	110 a	94 a	126 a	0.3 ab	157 a	4 a	45 a
Sorghum	18 b	94 ab	86 a	119 a	0.2 b	143 b	4 a	40 a
Wheat	22 ab	103 a	92 a	102 b	0.4 a	138 b	2 b	19 c

^a *Heliothis* phenotype from tobacco was collected by Dr. K. Klaus from Pangasinan. ^b In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^c DAS = days after sowing. ^d Growth index = no. of larvae becoming pupae (%) divided by mean developmental period (d). ^e Damaged grains = no. of grains with holes/450 grains × 100 (Note: the number of grains of 5 panicles was thinned to 450).

oviposition rate in 75-d-old rice plants could have been triggered by their floral nectar production.

Egg hatch was high, 86-94%. Newly hatched larvae readily fed on young leaves and soon dispersed. Larvae that were able to locate the panicles grew; those that failed, died.

Heliothis phenotypes from legumes and tobacco developed only to the 4th instar. Phenotypes reared from graminaceous crops — maize, sorghum, and wheat — developed completely. Rice and these crops may have similar

chemical constituents.

Development from egg to adult took 39-52 d. No additional molt (7th instar) that prolonged larval development was observed.

Host potential of rice was very low, with a 0.2-0.4 growth index, 79-126 mg larvae weight, 138-152 mg adult weight, and 24 d adult longevity.

The larval stages of all phenotypes damaged grain. In a no-choice test, larvae produced 19-45% damaged grains. The damage was similar to that made by *Conocephalus*. □

Pest Control and Management WEEDS

Evaluation of weed control methods in Bhutan

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Labor constraints can make timely weeding of rice crops difficult in Bhutan. We compared hand and rotary weeding with butachlor alone or supplemented with a single hand or rotary weeding. The trial was conducted at CARD in a split-plot design with three replications. Varieties Pusa 33 and IR36 were subplot

Effect of weed control method on rice yield. CARD, Wangdiphodrang, Bhutan, 1984.

Weed control method	Mean grain yield ^a (t/ha, 14% MC)			Weeding operation		RAVC ^e MBCR ^e (\$)	
	Pusa 33	IR36	Mean ^b	Time ^c (d/ha)	Cost ^d (\$/ha)		
	Rotary weeding 35 DT	5.9	6.0	5.9 bcd	16		13
Rotary weeding 21 and 40 DT	5.6	5.9	5.8 cd	22	18	1196	negative
Hand weeding 35 DT	5.2	5.6	5.4 d	27	22	1102	0
Hand weeding 21 and 40 DT	5.4	6.0	5.7 cd	53	44	1153	3.3
Butachlor 2 DT	6.3	1.2	6.8 abc	2	50	1368	10.5
Butachlor 2 DT + rotary weeding 35 DT	5.8	6.8	6.3 abcd	7	55	1270	6.1
Butachlor 2 DT + hand weeding 35 DT	6.5	6.6	6.5 ab	9	56	1317	7.3
Weedy check	4.2	4.8	4.5 e	-	-	-	-
Weed-free check	6.7	7.1	6.9 a	-	-	-	-

^a MC = moisture content. ^b Separation of means by DMRT at the 5% level. ^c Includes time taken to apply butachlor. ^d Based on a labor cost of \$0.83/day. Includes cost of butachlor at \$1.22/kg formulated product (5% granules). ^e Based on a rough rice price of \$0.21/kg.